

CHARACTERISTICS OF U-19 SOCCER PLAYERS IN VARIOUS ROLES

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Cite This Article: Dr. M. Suresh Kumar, "Characteristics of U-19 Soccer Players in Various Roles", *International Journal of Computational Research and Development*, International Peer Reviewed - Refereed Research Journal, Volume 9, Issue 1, January - June, Page Number 13-19, 2024.

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Abstract:

The purpose of the present study is to compare the selected, personality traits among soccer players at different playing positions. To achieve the purpose of the study, twenty (n=20) male soccer players were selected at random from each category of forwards, midfielders and defenders, a total of sixty (N=60) players were selected from the Tiruchirappalli. The age of the selected soccer players is restricted to U-19. The personality traits such as Psychoticism, extraversion, and neuroticism were selected as variables of this study. To assess the personality traits among soccer players, Eysenck Personality Questionnaire - Revised (EPQ-R) was used. To determine the significant differences analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used and the level of significance was tested at 0.05. From the results of the study it was concluded that there were no significant differences found in psychoticism trait and lie scale whereas significant differences found in extraversion and neuroticism traits among soccer players in different playing positions.

Key Words: Psychoticism, Extraversion and Neuroticism.

Introduction:

Association football, more commonly known as football or soccer, is a team sport played between two teams of eleven players with a spherical ball. It is played by more than 200 million players in over 200 countries and dependencies, making it the world's most popular sport. The game is played on a rectangular field with a goal post at each end. The object of the game is to score by getting the ball into the opponents' goal. Players are not allowed to touch the ball with their hands or arms other than goalkeepers (and then only when within their penalty area). Other players mainly use their feet to strike or pass the ball, but may also use any part of their body except the hands and the arms. The team that scores the maximum number of goals by the end of the match wins. If the score is level at the end of the game, either a draw is declared or the game goes into extra time or a penalty shootout depending on the format of the competition. The Laws of the Game were originally structured in England by The Football Association in 1863. Association football is governed internationally by the International Federation of Association Football (FIFA; French: Fédération Internationale de Football Association), which organizes World Cups for both men and women every four years. (Encyclopædia Britannica, 2008).

The dynamic organization within the individual of those psychophysical systems that determine his unique adjustments to his environment (Allport, 1937; Robbins et al., 2009). In simple words, personality can be defined as the collection of intrinsic and extrinsic traits that may affect the behavior of an individual. So to evaluate the personality of a person; traits or characteristics play the primary role (Allport, 1937; Bowers, 1973; John, 1990). In order to classify and present the personality traits that an individual possesses, numerous authors have presented the different trait theories. Psychoticism describes the personality as looking and liking abnormal, odd and unfamiliar things, aggressive to others sensation, lacking in sensation and responsiveness, cruel, troublesome and solitary. Neuroticism describes the personality as his or her obligation to neurotic collapse under stress, his or her emotional over-responsiveness and as a general emotional liability of an individual. Extraversion describes personality as sociable pro-clivition of individual, uninhibited, outspoken and out-going.

Review of Related Literature:

Najah and Rejeb (2015) investigated a study on selected psychological skills of male youth soccer players in different playing positions. This study examined possible positional differences of 180 male youth Tunisian soccer players between the ages of 15 and 19 years old from different clubs of 1st and 3rd Youth Class divisions. The subjects were divided into three playing positions, namely, forward (n = 60), midfield (n = 60) and defense (n = 60), and compared with regard to twelve psychological skills measured by means of the Ottawa Mental Skills Assessment Tool (OMSAT-3) of Durand Bush et al. (2001). Results yielded significant differences between basic and psychosomatic subscale scores of the players in different playing positions. Sérgio Adriano Gomes et.al (2016). The present study aimed to identify the psychological profiles of professional futsal players in terms of the gender schema and to evaluate the physiological parameters (speed, acceleration, strength, and power) and fatigue index of these athletes according to their gender profiles and relative to their positions on the

court. The Masculine Inventory of the Self-concept Gender Schemas was used to classify the sample into typological groups, and the Running Anaerobic Sprint Test was used to measure the physiological parameters (speed, acceleration, strength, and power) and the fatigue index. The study sample was composed of 64 male professional futsal players who competed in the National Indoor Soccer league in 2013; the subjects had an average weight of 76.00 ± 6.7 kg. Among the athletes studied, 23 (35.9%) were classified as heteroschematic female, 22 (34.4%) as heteroschematic male, and 19 (29.7%) as isoschematic. Regarding their positions on the court, eleven were goalkeepers (17.2%), 13 (20.3%) were defenders, 28 (43.8%) were midfielders, and 12 (18.8%) were attackers. The players had similar weights even when belonging to different typological groups and having different positions in the court. The results of the physiological parameter analysis relative to typological group showed that, on average, high-level soccer players presented similar performance profiles in different rounds, as statistically significant differences were not found in any of the studied physiological variables (weight, distance, speed, acceleration, strength, power, and fatigue index).

Statement of the Problem:

The purpose of the present study was to compare the personality traits among soccer players at different playing positions.

Methods:

The purpose of the present study is to compare the selected, personality traits among soccer players at different playing positions. To achieve the purpose of the study, twenty (n=20) male soccer players were selected at random from each category of forwards, midfielders and defenders, a total of sixty (N=60) players were selected from the Tiruchirappalli. The age of the selected soccer players is restricted to U-19. The personality traits such as Psychoticism, extraversion, and neuroticism were selected as variables of this study. To assess the personality traits among soccer players, Eysenck Personality Questionnaire - Revised (EPQ-R) was used. The EPQ measures the traits of personality: Psychoticism (P), (Extraversion), Neuroticism (N) and Lie (L). Reliability ranges are 0.80 to 0.90 and validity of the test is satisfactory.

Analysis of Data:

The data collected from the soccer players on selected Criterion variables were statistically examined by using analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the difference in personality traits among soccer players at different playing positions. The level of significance was tested at 0.05 level and the calculations were performed using SPSS version 20.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Psychoticism among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Forwards	20	14.4500	2.43818	.54519	13.3089	15.5911
Midfielders	20	14.2500	2.59301	.57981	13.0364	15.4636
Defenders	20	12.7000	2.45164	.54820	11.5526	13.8474
Total	60	13.8000	2.57629	.33260	13.1345	14.4655

Table 1 shows that the descriptive statistics of psychoticism for forwards N=20, Mean=14.45 and S.D. = 2.43, mid-fielders N=20, Mean=14.25 and S.D. = 2.59 and defenders N=20, Mean=12.70 and S.D. = 2.45.

Table 1 (A): Computation of Anova for Psychoticism among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

Psychoticism					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	36.700	2	18.350	2.947	.061
Within Groups	354.900	57	6.226		
Total	391.600	59			

The scores of psychoticism trait were analyzed among soccer players at different playing positions and the obtained F ratio is 2.94 for the df (2,57). In this case, since the P value is greater than 0.05 ($P > 0.05$) the significant difference does not exist.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Extraversion among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Forwards	20	11.6000	2.18608	.48882	10.5769	12.6231
Midfielders	20	12.7000	2.45164	.54820	11.5526	13.8474
Defenders	20	9.8000	1.28145	.28654	9.2003	10.3997
Total	60	11.3667	2.33591	.30157	10.7632	11.9701

Table 2 shows that the descriptive statistics of extraversion for forwards N=20, Mean=11.60 and S.D. = 2.18, mid-fielders N=20, Mean=12.70 and S.D. = 2.45 and defenders N=20, Mean=9.80 and S.D. = 1.28.

Table 2 (A): Computation of Anova for Extraversion among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

Extraversion					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	85.733	2	42.867	10.345	.000
Within Groups	236.200	57	4.144		
Total	321.933	59			

The extraversion trait were analyzed among soccer players at different playing positions and the obtained F ratio is 10.34 for the df (2,57). In this case, since the P value is lesser than 0.05 (P<0.05) the significant difference does exist.

Table 2 (B): Computation of Scheffe's Post-Hoc Test for Extraversion among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

Dependent Variable: Extraversion						
Scheffe						
(I) Football Playing Position	(J) Football Playing Position	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Forwards	Midfielders	-1.10000	.64373	.241	-2.7180	.5180
	Defenders	1.80000*	.64373	.026	.1820	3.4180
Midfielders	Forwards	1.10000	.64373	.241	-.5180	2.7180
	Defenders	2.90000*	.64373	.000	1.2820	4.5180
Defenders	Forwards	-1.80000*	.64373	.026	-3.4180	-.1820
	Midfielders	-2.90000*	.64373	.000	-4.5180	-1.2820

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The results of scheffe's post hoc test reveal that the mean difference between forwards and defenders, midfielders and defenders are 1.80 and 2.90 respectively which is found to be significant since P <0.05. The mean difference between forwards and midfielders is 1.10 and no significant difference does exist since P >0.05.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Neuroticism among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Forwards	20	12.2500	2.71206	.60643	10.9807	13.5193
Midfielders	20	12.7000	2.45164	.54820	11.5526	13.8474
Defenders	20	10.7000	2.07998	.46510	9.7265	11.6735
Total	60	11.8833	2.53846	.32771	11.2276	12.5391

Table 3 shows that the descriptive statistics of extraversion for forwards N=20, Mean=12.25 and S.D. = 2.71, mid-fielders N=20, Mean=12.70 and S.D. = 2.45 and defenders N=20, Mean=10.70 and S.D. = 2.07.

Table 3 (A): Computation of Anova for Neuroticism among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

Neuroticism					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	44.033	2	22.017	3.733	.030
Within Groups	336.150	57	5.897		
Total	380.183	59			

The scores of neuroticism trait were analyzed among soccer players at different playing positions and the obtained F ratio is 3.73 for the df (2,57). In this case, since the P value is lesser than 0.05 (P<0.05) the significant difference does exist.

Table 3 (B): Computation of Scheffe's Post-Hoc Test for Neuroticism among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

Dependent Variable: Neuroticism						
Scheffe						
(I) Football Playing Position	(J) Football Playing Position	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Forwards	Midfielders	-.45000	.76794	.843	-2.3802	1.4802

	Defenders	1.55000	.76794	.140	-.3802	3.4802
Midfielders	Forwards	.45000	.76794	.843	-1.4802	2.3802
	Defenders	2.00000*	.76794	.041	.0698	3.9302
Defenders	Forwards	-1.55000	.76794	.140	-3.4802	.3802
	Midfielders	-2.00000*	.76794	.041	-3.9302	-.0698

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The results of scheffe's post hoc test reveal that the mean difference between midfielders and defenders is 2.00 which is found to be significant, since $P < 0.05$. The mean difference between forwards and midfielders, forwards and defenders, are -.45 and 1.55 respectively and no significant difference does exist since $P > 0.05$.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Lie Scale Among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Forwards	20	10.6500	1.34849	.30153	10.0189	11.2811
Midfielders	20	10.5000	1.05131	.23508	10.0080	10.9920
Defenders	20	9.8000	1.28145	.28654	9.2003	10.3997
Total	60	10.3167	1.26881	.16380	9.9889	10.6444

Table 4 shows that the descriptive statistics of Lie Scale for forwards $N=20$, Mean=10.65 and S.D. = 1.34, mid-fielders $N=20$, Mean=10.50 and S.D. = 1.05 and defenders $N=20$, Mean=9.80 and S.D. = 1.28.

Table 4 (A): Computation of Anova for Lie Scale among Soccer Players at Different Playing Positions

Liescale					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	8.233	2	4.117	2.705	.075
Within Groups	86.750	57	1.522		
Total	94.983	59			

The scores of lie scale were analyzed among soccer players at different playing positions and the obtained F ratio is 2.70 for the df (2,57). In this case, since the P value is greater than 0.05 ($P > 0.05$) the significant difference does not exist.

Figure 1: Mean scores of Psychoticism

Figure 2: Mean scores of Extraversion

Figure 3: Mean scores of Neuroticism

Figure 4: Mean scores of lie scale

Conclusions:

Within the limitations of the study the following conclusions were drawn:

- There were no significant differences found in psychoticism trait and lie scale among soccer players in different playing positions.

- There was significant difference exists in extraversion and neuroticism traits among soccer players in different playing positions.

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